

КЛАСИЧНІ ПІДХОДИ ФОРМУВАННЯ АРТИСТИЧНИХ ЗДІБНОСТЕЙ МОЛОДШИХ ШКОЛЯРІВ НА ЗАНЯТТЯХ З ВОКАЛУ

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CLASSICAL APPROACHES TO THE FORMATION OF ARTISTIC ABILITIES OF JUNIOR SCHOOLCHILDREN IN VOCAL LESSONS

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Анотація

У статті висвітлено класичні підходи формування артистичних здібностей молодших школярів на заняттях з вокалу. На основі застосування широкого спектру методів (аналіз, синтез, узагальнення, систематизація) розглянуто теоретичні аспекти проблеми. Виокремлено класичні наукові підходи (системний, особистісно-орієнтований, діяльнісний та культурологічний) та здійснено їхню характеристику. Доведено значення означених підходів у формуванні артистичних здібностей молодших школярів на заняттях з вокалу.

Abstract

The article highlights the classical approaches to the formation of artistic abilities of junior schoolchildren in vocal lessons. Based on the use of a wide range of methods (analysis, synthesis, generalization, systematization), the theoretical aspects of the problem are considered. The classical scientific approaches (systemic, personality-oriented, activity-oriented and cultural) are singled out and characterized. The importance of these approaches in the formation of artistic abilities of junior schoolchildren in vocal lessons is proved.

Ключові слова: підхід, класичний підхід, молодші школярі, вокал, артистичні здібності.

Keywords: approach, classical approach, younger students, vocals, artistic abilities.

The formation of artistic abilities of junior schoolchildren is particularly dependent on scientific approaches. In general, thanks to scientific approaches, the author chooses a special research strategy on the basis of which his scientific outlook is based, and his views on the study of a particular research problem are focused. It is found that the approach is characterized as a set of principles, methods, ideas that influence the formation of the result of a particular issue. Moreover, an approach is a set of principles and methods that are unified in content. An approach is a methodology and ideology for solving research problems. From this perspective, we can state that the scientific approach, taking into account pedagogical, philosophical, and psychological prerequisites, provides the disclosure of the fundamental idea, main goals, stages, and principles [6].

That is why, when highlighting the problem of forming the artistic abilities of junior schoolchildren in vocal lessons, it is advisable to consider classical methodological approaches that are important to take into account during vocal lessons.

The analysis and systematization will make it possible to emphasize that the methodological basis of vocal lessons for junior pupils is a systematic approach. The latter is based on the methods of induction and synthesis and aims to optimize the system. The systemic approach requires considering the vocal training of younger students in its integrity and development [2].

The vocal lessons for younger students are holistic in nature. They include many technical and artistic elements that are aimed at solving the main task - expressive performance based on the accurate reproduction of a musical and poetic text. We state that all components of the vocal, technical and artistic order are interconnected and function systematically. As a result, the appropriate organization of the educational process is important for the formation of this systematic nature. The latter should be holistic and continuing.

Thus, a systematic approach should provide for the fundamentals of vocal performance as a set of vocal performance actions, not the sum of disparate vocal and technical elements. It should be noted that the pedagogical management of vocal lessons for junior pupils should be built from simple to complex.

Covering vocal lessons as a holistic process of forming the artistic abilities of junior schoolchildren, we focus on the personality of the students. That is why it is appropriate to highlight the personality-oriented approach, which substantiates the idea of the active, social, and creative essence of a person as a person [4].

The personality-oriented approach ensures competent and high-quality mastery of theoretical and practical skills of the younger generation.

It should be emphasized that within the framework of the personality-oriented approach, the formation of artistic abilities of primary school students in vocal lessons is also based on the natural process of self-development of musical abilities and creative potential of children. We explain this opinion by the fact that vocal

education does not aim to train a future professional singer. Moreover, the vocal abilities of younger students, as a manifestation of musical abilities, are usually different [3].

We have come to the conclusion that adherence to a personality-oriented approach in working with junior schoolchildren in vocal lessons affects the formation of not only the artistic abilities of students, but also the foundations of singing culture and the education of a creative personality. The purpose of vocal lessons is to prepare junior schoolchildren for artistic and valuable vocal performance, which is ensured by vocal and performance technique, development of children's voice data and comprehension of educational vocal material. It has been proved that the involvement of junior schoolchildren in the aesthetic values of vocal art is determined by the repertoire policy in the solo singing class. The latter involves the inclusion of highly artistic samples of children's vocal repertoire in the educational material [5].

One of the classical scientific approaches that is important to take into account when forming the artistic abilities of junior schoolchildren in vocal lessons is the activity approach. It has been established that activity is a crucial condition for personality development. From this point of view, there is a need to observe an activity-based approach in vocal lessons, which is closely interconnected with the personality-oriented one.

The activity approach is of particular importance for the formation of artistic abilities of junior pupils in vocal lessons. Since this approach involves the development of children's skills and abilities, as well as the application of the acquired knowledge in practical situations (concerts, performances) [1].

Characterizing some classical scientific approaches that are important in the process of forming artistic abilities of junior schoolchildren in vocal lessons, it is important to focus on the cultural approach. We can state that the cultural approach considers vocal lessons as a part of culture. Moreover, it focuses the educational process on the transfer of cultural, ideological, spiritual, and value orientations to younger students. The cultural approach ensures the emergence of a cultural environment. The latter is a condition for the self-realization of junior schoolchildren and influences the formation of their artistic abilities in the process of vocal training [7].

Covering the classical scientific approaches, in particular, systemic, personality-oriented, activity-oriented and cultural, we have found that the current educational vocal practice requires an innovative, modern methodology, the vector of which is aimed at orienting the participants of the educational process towards a large flow of information, the ability to implement it in practice, taking into account different conditions and states [6].

Thus, we conclude that the formation of artistic abilities of junior schoolchildren depends on the observance of a number of scientific approaches. It has been proved that classical scientific approaches, such as systemic, personality-oriented, activity-oriented, and cultural approaches, play a particularly important role in the development of artistic abilities of junior schoolchildren in vocal lessons.

The conducted research does not exhaust all aspects of the problem of classical approaches that should be followed in the formation of artistic abilities of junior schoolchildren in vocal lessons and shows the need for its further development in such promising areas as the principles and methods of forming artistic abilities of junior schoolchildren in vocal lessons.

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